

Automating Sensor Data *FAIRification* with the *Sensor Interfacing Language*

Streamlined development of *FAIR Sensor Services* using Model-Driven Software Engineering

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Abstract

The successful implementation of the *FAIR Guiding Principles* [1] heavily relies on standardized, interoperable data models using technologies from the *Semantic Web* [2], [3], [4], such as ontologies and standardized vocabulary. However, fully semantically interoperable data models or ontologies bear high complexity hindering their application by researchers, such as engineers, who are not familiar with the concepts from the *Semantic Web* [5]. To lower the barrier for implementing the *FAIR Guiding Principles*, we developed the *Sensor Interfacing Language* (SOIL) [6], a light-weight domain-specific modeling language for describing the data model of any arbitrary sensor or measuring system. Based on a textual description with an intuitive syntax and grammar [7], inspired by JSON, Turtle, and Python, researchers can easily document the features of a sensor or measuring system via the publicly accessible *SOIL Editor*¹. Employing model-driven software engineering (MDSE), the SOIL model can be automatically translated into a full data model based on *Semantic Web* standards, such as RDF and OWL. Thus, researchers do not have to deal with the complexity of the semantic sensor model, as they never come into direct contact with it. Parsing, validation, and translation of SOIL models is carried out using the *SOIL Workbench*, deployed and running in the background of the *SOIL Editor*. Metadata profile are automatically generated out of a SOIL model, which enables automated compliance tests of acquired data.

Moreover, MDSE enables the generation of interfaces for various different communication protocols and data formats, which is required to significantly increase the accessibility of the measurement data provided [8], [9]. This streamlines the development and implementation of cyber-physical measuring systems (CPMSs) as shown in Figure 1. Thereby, *Separation-of-Concerns* [10] is realized, which effectively decouples the implementation of the three layers of the *FAIR Sensor Service* [11]. Finally, semantic interoperability, i.e. “use of formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable

¹<https://purl.org/soil-editor>

language for knowledge representation” [1], is ensured by the SOIL-based *FAIRification*. Technical interoperability, i.e., accessibility, is guaranteed by the unified network interface of the *FAIR Sensor Service* using standardized, open, free and universal communication protocols, namely HTTP, MQTT, and OPC UA, and data formats, such as JSON and XML or JSON-LD and Turtle for data modeled according to RDF.

Figure 1. The effortful status quo of describing sensor data and deploying measuring systems is shown on the left. The right half shows the provision of FAIR sensor data and the (partially) automated deployment of a FAIR Sensor Service due to standardized data modeling based on the SOIL.

The developed tools reduced the deployment of new measuring equipment at our institute significantly and increased the accessibility and (re-)usability of acquired data. This improvement has been achieved by the implementation of an automated data acquisition pipeline shown in Figure 2 based on the standardized data models and communication interfaces of *FAIR Sensor Services*.

Figure 2. The pipeline for automated measurement data acquisition at WLZ of RWTH Aachen University based on SOIL and FAIR Sensor Services. Access to live data is implemented using MQTT also used for automatically storing the data to an InfluxDB [12] and preserving long-term accessibility and re-usability. An automated data archiving to Coscine [13] based on the generated metadata profiles is under development. The mapping to the steps of the Research Data Management (RDM) life cycle [14] in the left lower corner are indicated by colors.

The *FAIRness* of sensor data acquired with *FAIR Sensor Service* has been assessed using *FAIRness* assessment frameworks, namely *F-UJI* [15], *FAIR Checker* [2], and *FAIR enough* [16]. The individual *FAIRness* scores for acquired metadata, data and metadata profiles have been normalized to a percentage scale for comparison. Compared to publicly available assessments of foreign research data using *FAIR enough*, *SOIL* and *FAIR Sensor Services* significantly increase the *FAIRness* of acquired sensor data by a factor of 1.7 [17]. Lastly, *SOIL* and *FAIR Sensor Services* are applicable beyond engineering in any domain using sensors or measuring systems, such as natural and life sciences, and thereby bridge the gap between distinct consortia with interoperable data models and enable cross-domain re-use of research data.

Acronyms

CPMS	cyber-physical measuring system
DSML	domain-specific modeling language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
MDSE	model-driven software engineering
MP	metadata profile
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
OPC UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PyPi	Python Package Index
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDM	Research Data Management
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SOIL	<i>Sensor Interfacing Language</i>
UI	user interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Resources

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Metadata Profile for FAIR Sensor Data Based on the Sensor Interfacing Language

Metadata profiles of the sensor data model of *SOIL* in *SHACL*. The most current machine-actionable metadata profiles are available at <https://purl.org/soil/>.

Dataset, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10965203>

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Validation and FAIRness assessment results of FAIR Sensor Services based on the SensOr Interfacing Language

This dataset contains the scripts and the raw output of the automated *FAIRness* assessment.

Dataset & Software, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13835237>

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Python Unified Device Interface

The implemented Python library for running a *FAIR Sensor Service*. It can directly be installed via the Python Package Index (PyPi) using `pip wzl-udi`.

Software, V 10.1.1, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922866>

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SOIL Dummies

The SOIL models, handwritten source code, and the generated metadata profiles and static metadata sets of the three simulated measuring systems implemented as *FAIR Sensor Services* used for validation of the developed models, SOIL and the implemented libraries.

Software, 1.0.0, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13831871>

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SOIL Workbench

Language workbench implementing the parser, validator, and generator for SOIL based on the *MontiCore* language workbench developed by Rumpe et al. [18].

Software, V2.3.1, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922911>

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SOIL Editor

Web-based user interface (UI) for intuitively defining interface descriptions of *FAIR Sensor Services* using SOIL.

Software, V1.0.0, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922935>

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SOIL Backend

FastAPI-based Python server encapsulating the command line interface of the *SOIL Workbench*. Primarily used as the backend in conjunction with the *SOIL Editor* providing a web-based UI for developing interfaces for *FAIR Sensor Services* based on the SOIL.

Software, V1.0.0, Zenodo, 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12513293>

Author contributions

Matthias Bodenbenner: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing

Mark P. Sanders: Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization

Dominik Wolfschläger: Project administration, Supervision, Writing - review & editing

Robert H. Schmitt: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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